

Characterization Form

Please answer the questions below regarding your experience working with Micro Frontends:

1. What is your e-mail?

2. How much experience do you have working with Software Development?

- a. Up to 1 year
- b. Between 1 and 2 years
- c. Between 2 and 3 years
- d. Between 3 and 4

3. How much experience do you have working with Micro Frontends?

- a. Up to 1 year
- b. Between 1 and 2 years
- c. Between 2 and 3 years
- d. Between 3 and 4

4. What role(s) do you hold in the development team?

- a. Web Developer
- b. Mobile Developer
- c. Backend Developer
- d. Full Stack Developer (web, mobile, backend)
- e. Software Architect
- f. Tech Lead
- g. Project Lead
- h. Other: _____

5. Which team do you work on (masked)?

- a. A
- b. B
- c. C
- d. D
- e. E
- f. F
- g. G
- h. H

6. In what ways have you worked with Micro Frontends?

- a. Implementation of features in existing Micro Frontends
- b. Bug fixing in an existing architecture
- c. Addition of new Micro Frontends
- d. Migration from a monolithic frontend to Micro Frontends
- e. Evaluation and/or inspection of Micro Frontends
- f. Other: _____

7. How did you acquire knowledge about Micro Frontends?

- a. Practical, by joining a company that already implemented Micro Frontends
- b. Practical, by creating a personal project focused on Micro Frontends
- c. Theoretical, by watching videos and reading books about Micro Frontends
- d. Theoretical, by researching Micro Frontends on programming websites and forums (Stack Overflow, Medium, GitHub, etc.)
- e. Other: _____

8. Do you use any tools or support materials during Micro Frontends development? If so, which ones?